

Polyhedra. HPC Optimisation of SDLPS distributed Simulator

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Abstract

An unambiguous formal description of a model is one of the main challenges in simulation. In the area of social simulation, model conceptualisation is usually performed verbally creating a potential for translation errors between the conceptual model and its codification in a programming language. Here we present a simulator based on the SDLP and optimised for HPC environment that facilitates this process. The two main advantages of using SDLP for model description are the ease of communication between the context specialist and the programmer thanks to the visual interface and the full and unambiguous codification of the model enabling its execution in any environment. By optimising the simulator for HPC environments, the Polyhedra project has opened a new range of possibilities for computationally intensive models typical for social science applications.

1. Introduction

Model conceptualization provides a description of the main causal relations between the different elements of a simulation model, enabling its translation into code and aiding the validation, verification and posterior accreditation phases required in any modelling project.

In social simulation area, the conceptualization of a simulation model, often performed in natural language (verbally) may lack the full unambiguity thus preventing a complete codification of the model. As a result, the translation from the conceptual model to computer code is prone to errors. In addition, in the frame of High-Performance Computing (HPC), the codification of a model must follow specific rules to enable parallelization of the code and to make use of specific libraries. The unawareness of these libraries by context specialists who usually define the model makes it almost impossible for an automatic codification of a simulation that can be executed in an HPC environment.

In this white paper, we present the results obtained within the frame of the European PRACE SHAPE programme [1] funded project “HPC optimization of SDLPS distributed simulator” awarded to Polyhedra Tech SL and the Barcelona Supercomputing Center in 2018. The project team has developed a robust methodology that allows users to represent a conceptual model of a simulated system, using a metamodeling language, the Specification and Description Language (SDL), that simplifies or automatizes the generation of code to be executed in an HPC environment.

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The SDL language [2] lies at the core of the project. Specification and Description Language (SDL) is an object-oriented formal and graphical language defined by the International Telecommunications Union–Telecommunications Standardization Sector (ITU–T) in the Z. 100 recommendation. From its origins, SDL was designed for the specification of event-oriented, real-time and interactive complex systems. These systems might involve different concurrent activities that use signals to perform communication. The SDL consists of four levels to describe the structure and the behaviour of the models: system, blocks, processes and procedures. More details about the Specification and Description Language can be found in the recommendation Z.100 [3] or at the web site [4].

The objectives of the project were twofold. First, to investigate novel parallelization strategies that can leverage an HPC platform such as the BSC supercomputer *Marenostrum 4* to accelerate the simulator runtime. Second, to test, benchmark and optimise the simulator on social science models requiring particular parallelization paradigms. Thus, opening the HPC capacity to a new group of users while at the same time increasing the robustness of their software by improving the level of documentation, verification and validation of the models. To that end two the Polyhedra and the BSC teams have developed two tools: i) model-compiler libraries and ii) a simulator.

2. Deliverables

The tools needed to generate the C++ code that can be executed in the HPC environment consist of a model-compiler and a simulator. The former takes care of reading the XML generated by SDLPS (the SDL simulation framework) that represents the model and runs several tests in order to ensure the model is correct. The latter is the infrastructure that will manage the runtime execution of the model allowing to run certain parts of the simulation in parallel whilst keeping the results the same as if it was executed sequentially.

Model-compiler libraries

This tool is responsible for translating the XML files representing an SDL model into a C++ source file that can be integrated into the simulator. It consists of three phases:

1. The first phase reads all the information from the root file of the project and gathers all the information needed by the next phase. This phase performs basic checks like ensuring that files exist.
2. The second phase performs additional checks to ensure the model is semantically correct and generates additional information about the model needed by the final phase. For example: which processes can communicate among themselves, which process may potentially create other processes in the execution, etc. This information will be used by the simulator to guarantee correct executions.
3. The third phase is responsible for materializing all the information about the model gathered through the previous phases into a C++ source file.

Figure 1 shows a simplified version of the code generated for PManager.

```

1 struct Bprime_PManager : public Process {
2     int N = 100;
3     int P = 3;
4     ...
5     enum State {
6         END,
7         PREPARING,
8     };
9     State state;
10    Process_Inst num_instance;
11    // Process initialization function
12    void init();
13    // Process event handler function
14    void specific_step(shared_ptr<Event>& e);
15    static int total_instances;
16 };
17 int Bprime_PManager::total_instances = 0;
18
19 void Bprime_PManager::init() {
20     sqrtN=sqrt(N);
21     S = (N-(sqrtN+1)) / P;
22     R = (N-(sqrtN+1)) % P;
23     L = sqrtN + i*S + 1;
24     H = L+S-1 + (i < R);
25
26     shared_ptr<NEW_SEGMENT_event>
27     send_event(new NEW_SEGMENT_event);
28     send_event->tsrc = time; send_event->delay = 1;
29     // Send NEW_SEGMENT to SELF
30     sim_send(this, send_event);
31
32     state = PREPARING;
33 }
34 void Bprime_PManager::specific_step(shared_ptr<Event>& e) {
35     switch (state) {
36     case END:
37         switch (e->type) {
38         case Event_type::PARTIAL_RESULTS:
39             shared_ptr<PARTIAL_RESULTS_event> e1 = e;
40             list2 = e1->list2; H = e1->H; L = e1->L;
41
42             ReportList2(list2, c, H, L);
43
44             state = END;
45             break;
46         }
47     case PREPARING:
48         switch (e->type) {
49         case Event_type::NEW_SEGMENT:
50             shared_ptr<NEW_SEGMENT_event> e1 = e;
51             if (i<P) {
52                 {
53                     shared_ptr<SEGMENT_event> send_event(new SEGMENT_event);
54                     // Timestamp = tsrc + delay
55                     send_event->tsrc = time; send_event->delay = 1;
56                     send_event->type = Event_type::SEGMENT;
57                     // Setup event data to send
58                     send_event->i = i; send_event->L = L;
59                     send_event->H = H; send_event->P = P;
60                     send_event->R = R;
61                     // Send to Psegment instance '\\i\\'
62                     auto p = proc_instances[PKind::Bprime_PSegment][i];
63                     sim_send(p, send_event);
64                 }
65                 ...
66                 // Send SKIP and NEW_SEGMENT events
67                 ...
68                 i++;
69                 L = H+1;
70                 H = L+S-1 + (i < R);
71                 state = PREPARING;
72             } else {
73                 state = END;
74             }
75             break;
76         }
77     }
78     break;
79 }
80 }
81 }

```

Figure 1: PManager C++ code simplified output.

Simulator

This tool implements two compatible simulation environments able to execute the model in the C++ source file: one sequential and one parallel. The sequential simulation runs the simulation without any use of parallelism. On the other hand, the parallel implementation can run parts of the simulation concurrently by using OpenMP [5] if several conditions are met.

Each process P has one external event queue Q_R for each process R connected to P . P has also an additional event queue Q_{self} for events it sends to itself. A process P can send events to other processes, but these events will have a timestamp greater or equal to the timestamp of the last event that was received by P , we call this timestamp L_P . Moreover, the sequence of events sent from P to R must have nondecreasing timestamps. For each external event queue Q_K in P , there are one or more events with a timestamp M_K that is larger or equal than the other events. We define the critical time T_{crit} of a process P as the minimum of all the M_K timestamps. A process P can be simulated concurrently with other processes if it has events in its queues whose timestamp is lower than T_{crit} .

Figure 2: Example of parallel process.

Process P1 is connected to P2 and P3 and has events to be consumed. From P2 it has events e1, e2, e3 with timestamps 3, 10 and 11 respectively, whereas from P3 it has e5, e6, e7 with timestamps 5, 6 and 7. In addition, P1 has an event e4 sent to itself with timestamp 3. Figure 2 shows an example of this process.

The T_{crit} of P1 is $\min(e3, e7) = 7$. In this example P1 can execute in parallel the events with time e1, e4, e5, e6 marked as red. That is because P2 and P3 only can send events with timestamp greater equal 11 and 7 respectively.

In order to be able to detect this situation, the parallel simulator has an inspection and execution phase. The former goes through the current list of processes in the system, gathering the ones able to run in parallel while searches the process owning the minimum timestamp event. The later runs in parallel the processes gathered in case that more than one has been found. If not, the process with the minimum timestamp event is executed.

3. Use cases

For verifications of the HPC library developed to directly execute SDL models in HPC environments, we replicated two standard simulation models: numerical simulation and an agent-based model. The objective of the former, *the Sieve of Eratosthenes model*, is to verify the implementation of the library and to test the robustness of the process. The agent-based model is a replication of a seminal model in social sciences *the Artificial Anasazi model*. Here, it is used to test the potential of the proposed workflow to facilitate communication in a multidisciplinary team. The hope is that the SDL language can become a bridge between scientists and engineers working on complex simulation models.

Sieve of Eratosthenes model

The prime number model is based on a parallel version of the Sieve of Eratosthenes [6] method to calculate the prime numbers on a segment. To do so an important element is to detail the structure of the model since this structure will facilitate the parallelization of the algorithm in the HPC environment. The structure of the model comprises the SYSTEM and one BLOCK “Bprime”. The Bprime BLOCK contains the three main PROCESSES that will be used to calculate the prime numbers, “PCreator”, “PManager” and “PSegment”.

In order to take advantage of the parallelism condition of the simulator, the model follows four well-defined phases. First, PCreator creates P processes PSegment ready to get work. Second, PManager distributes the chunks of the sieve to all PSegments sending the boundaries for each one. In order to satisfy the parallelism condition, a SKIP message is also sent with a higher timestamp. This will make the simulator aware that all

PSegments can run in parallel and execute them. Third, PSegments compute the partial sieve and send the results to PManager. To ensure the results are printed in order, each PSegment sends the data with a timestamp plus a delay equal to its process instance. Finally, PManager processes each message sequentially printing the results.

Once the program is executed the results are written in the output files. The result obtained of computing the sieve between 2 and 1000 using 5 PSegments is shown in (Figure 3).

```
$ cat primers_6952114.out
NOTE: 5 can run in parallel
NOTE: 5 can run in parallel
2 3 5 7 11 13 17 19 23 29 31 37 41 43 47 53 59 61 67 71 73 79 83 89 97 101 103 107 109 113 127 131 137 139 149 151 157 163
167 173 179 181 191 193 197 199 211 223 227 229 233 239 241 251 257 263 269 271 277 281 283 293 307 311 313 317 331 337 347
349 353 359 367 373 379 383 389 397 401 409 419 421 431 433 439 443 449 457 461 463 467 479 487 491 499 503 509 521 523 541
547 557 563 569 571 577 587 593 599 601 607 613 617 619 631 641 643 647 653 659 661 673 677 683 691 701 709 719 727 733 739
743 751 757 761 769 773 787 797 809 811 821 823 827 829 839 853 857 859 863 877 881 883 887 907 911 919 929 937 941 947 953
967 971 977 983 991 997
```

Figure 3: Example of an output.

The Artificial Anasazi model

The Artificial Anasazi model [7] is a well-known model within the agent-based modelling community. It describes the population dynamics of the Pueblo Peoples who lived in the Long House Valley, Arizona between AD 800 and AD 1350. The model simulates population fluctuations and spatial distribution of human settlements on the landscape as a result of climatic shifts and individual decision-making process.

The aim of using this highly complex agent-based model was to test the viability of using the SDL language as the ‘communication platform’ with a highly challenging context likely to mirror real-world circumstances of a diverse group of stakeholders or clients. Throughout the modelling process a specialist in social simulation has collaborated closely with computer science engineers to translate the model’s ontology, to develop the model’s implementation and in solving the barriers preventing it from efficient parallelization of the code and other issues that needed to be overcome for the model to be executed in an HPC environment. The discussion between the context specialist (the social scientist) and HPC specialists was significantly facilitated since all of them shared the same basis: the SDL graphical model. The full results of the reimplementing of the Artificial Anasazi model and the benefits of using the SDL framework while working in multidisciplinary teams will be further reported in an academic paper at a later time.

Conclusions

Thanks to the PRACE SHAPE programme we have been able to develop, test and apply a computational tool enabling model definition in the SDL language and its execution in HPC environment. This has streamlined the SDLPS parallelization capacity and significantly increased its attractiveness and usability for end users with different HPC capacities and different levels of HPC expertise available to them. The testing and integration of social science models undertaken during the project aim to extend the target audience of the simulator. Wider application of the SDL (a formal, graphical, unambiguous and complete modelling language) has a potential for streamlining, automating and documenting the process of simulation design and development among non-academics and within academic fields where the level of computational expertise is low (e.g., social sciences, humanities). The combination of the easy to understand graphical model description with the computational capacity of HPC gives this tool users the ability to solve real-world problems by quickly designing and implementing complex models and running them using HPC tools without the need for an extensive team of

computer science experts. The hope is that the project will open up the tool to a new set of clients while providing them with access to state-of-the-art technology which was unavailable for them until now.

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